

Semi-Annual Lesson Report:
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Civilian Harm Mitigation & Response (CHMR)
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Property Reconstruction and Restitution: A Fundamental Stabilization Issue with Ukraine as Case Study (JLLIS ID# 239637)

Observation

With over 14 million people now displaced from their housing, land, and property (HLP) in Ukraine¹¹⁹ there is considerable concern about the reconstruction and restitution process. This is particularly significant in Ukraine given that destruction of HLP appears a purposeful effort on the part of Russian forces.

The Ukrainian Prime Minister emphasized the importance of reconstruction and restitution planning before the war is over. As early as July 2022, Ukraine and Western countries began discussion about frozen Russian assets use as part of this effort.¹²⁰ With such early planning, Ukraine may become a model for rapid and transparent post-war reconstruction. As a case study, Ukraine provides an overview of some of the challenges and opportunities of a forward-focused robust HLP mass claims process for restitution and compensation.¹²¹

Discussion

Large-scale population dislocation from housing, land, and property (HLP) due to armed conflict leads to:

- 1) the creation of population-wide grievances that can influence the course of a war and post-war stability;
- 2) trafficking in HLP to fund belligerent activities;
- 3) negative impacts on economic recovery;
- 4) distrust in institutions and governance; and
- 5) the creation of alternative ethnic, tribal, religious, or sect-based approaches to reclaiming and securing HLP for specific constituencies at the expense of others.¹²²

As well, the larger-scale connections between HLP and territorial claims are robust. However, if managed well, HLP restitution and compensation processes can lay the groundwork for durable peace, effective governance, and the investment and productive international relations needed for successful recovery of population stability.¹²³

¹¹⁹ Edith Lederer, "Russian invasion displaced 14 million Ukrainians, according to U.N. report," *PBS News Hour*, November 2, 2022, <https://www.pbs.org/newshour/world/russian-invasion-displaced-14-million-ukrainians-according-to-u-n-report> (accessed January 23, 2023).

¹²⁰ "Denys Shmyhal: The main source of Ukraine's recovery should be the confiscated assets of Russia," *State sites of Ukraine*, July 4, 2022, <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/en/news/denys-shmyhal-osnovnym-dzherelom-vidnovlennia-ukrainy-povyvnyi-staty-konfiskovani-aktyvy-rosii> (accessed January 23, 2023).

¹²¹ Yuliya Panfil, Jon Unruh, and Michael Cholod, "How to Get Displaced Ukrainians Back Into Their Homes Quickly," *Slate*, October 4, 2022, <https://slate.com/technology/2022/10/ukraine-war-counteroffensive-displaced-people-homes.html> (accessed January 23, 2023).

¹²² Jon Unruh and R.C. Williams, "Land: A foundation for peacebuilding," in *Land and post-conflict peacebuilding*, ed. J. Unruh and R.C. Williams, (London: Earthscan, 2013), <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781849775793-8/land-foundation-peacebuilding-jon-unruh-rhodri-williams> (accessed February 1, 2023); Jon Unruh, "Housing, Land, and Property Rights as War-Financing Stability Commodities: A Typology with Lessons from Darfur, Colombia and Syria," *Stability: International Journal of Security & Development* 10(1): 1 (2022), 1-19, <http://doi.org/10.5334/sta.811> (accessed February 2, 2023).

¹²³ Jon Unruh and R.C. Williams, "Land: A foundation for peacebuilding."; Pablo Kalmanovitz, "Compensation and Land Restitution in Transitions from War to Peace," in *Rationality, Democracy and Justice: The Legacy of Jon Elster*, ed. Claudio Lopez-Guerra and Julia Maskivker (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 191-219 https://www.academia.edu/11513323/Compensation_and_Land_Restitution_in_Transitions_from_War_to_Peace_in

The return of war-dislocated populations to their HLP is always a daunting process, particularly when their properties are damaged or destroyed and they need compensation for reconstruction or housing alternatives. War returnees often cannot prove they are the rightful occupants because records are missing, destroyed, inaccurate, no longer valid, or never existed. In Ukraine, its fraught transition from the Soviet property model to private property makes this especially complicated. Prior to the Russian invasion, Ukraine's property registry was only 40 percent complete. This means more than half of the population is unlikely to have formal records of their property rights.

For Ukrainian residents that fled, their property may be occupied or claimed by others. This appears as a reality in eastern Ukraine since Putin staged annexations of occupied Ukrainian territories, and Russian allied militias use abandoned HLP as forms of payment to its personnel.¹²⁴ In other countries and conflicts, such a scenario has meant that mass dislocations lasted decades and even generations. In the meantime, HLP can change hands several times and become legally held by others, including political elites or opposed ethnic, sectarian, or religious groups. Meanwhile, the grievances of displaced families build, sometimes erupting into political or insurgent movements.

And yet, despite the large-scale population dislocation it faces, Ukraine has the potential to transform the difficult postwar return process. With an advanced digital infrastructure supporting a digitally sophisticated population, significant smartphone penetration, and a government willing to innovate, Ukraine may become the first postwar country in which millions of displaced citizens can return quickly and be compensated promptly and fairly for HLP damaged or destroyed in the war.

First, Ukraine must modify the compensation law currently in review. The current legal proposal suggests HLP compensation decisions be made one-by-one as it would in a stable setting. This process would take generations to complete. It also proposes specific documentary evidence of ownership—i.e., property records—to qualify for compensation. But with more than half the country lacking formal property documentation, large numbers of legitimate claims risk rejection by such a requirement which will lead to significant grievances. In contrast, other war-affected restitution cases allow for alternative forms of evidence for HLP claims such as electricity and water bills, called *non-party evidence*.¹²⁵ Non-party evidence is created constantly, just by virtue of living in the digital age. In digitally advanced Ukraine, these records are readily available.

Second, while proof of HLP ownership is important, so is the submission of it. Again, technology can help. Ukrainians need a digital platform that allows them to file HLP compensation claims without requiring them to create an account that could be used to target them if their smartphone or computer fell into the wrong hands, especially as Russian forces are known to confiscate these from civilians. Ukraine's Ministry of Digital Transformation took a critical step to reconfigure its

[Claudio Lopez Guerra and Julia Maskivker eds Rationality Democracy and Justice The Legacy of Jon Elster 2015](#) (accessed February 2, 2023); and Agnes Hurwitz, Kaysie Studdard, and Rhodri Williams, *Housing, Land, Property and Conflict Management: Identifying Policy Options for Rule of Law Programming*, (New York, NY: International Peace Institute, 2005), <https://www.ipinst.org/2005/10/housing-land-property-and-conflict-management-identifying-policy-options-for-rule-of-law-programming> (accessed February 2, 2023).

¹²⁴ Kseniya Kirillova, "Visitors from Russia pushing out Donbas locals and taking over housing," *Radio Liberty*, January 1, 2018, <https://euromaidanpress.com/2018/01/27/visitors-from-russia-pushing-out-donbas-locals-and-taking-over-housing/> (accessed February 2, 2023).

¹²⁵ Lesson author's note: *Non-party evidence* is that held by a party different from the claimant, but which corroborates the claim.

Diia digital services platform to allow citizens to submit property damage claims, and already more than 240,000 have done so. But *Diia* needs to take in a much wider range of evidence of property ownership, rental and other forms of occupancy, and be encrypted so that claimants remain anonymous and untraceable to those outside the claims process.

Finally, Ukraine needs a way to pay for what will be very large amounts of HLP compensation, reconstruction, building alternative HLP, and the needed scale-up in capacity to conduct the restitution/compensation process—ideally using money from seized Russian assets.

Recommendations

There is significant interest within a large portion of the international community and the government of Ukraine to begin now on the preparations for large-scale HLP restitution and compensation processes for the millions of displaced families. A November 2022 vote at the UN General Assembly called upon willing states to begin reconstruction preparations now. The enormity of the increasing reconstruction cost, currently estimated at USD 1.3 trillion, suggests the international community will have an interest in the repurposing of Russian assets for reconstruction. This is particularly true given the expected reluctance of Western nation taxpayers to pay for Ukraine's reconstitution when there is a perception that the aggressor state should, and in this case can, do so.¹²⁶ As an example, Canada recently passed a law allowing for the repurposing of frozen Russian assets for Ukraine's reconstruction, with the United States (US) and other countries pursuing similar legislation.¹²⁷

The relevant international community should work with the government of Ukraine to engage in a set of known best practices for the HLP mass claims process, with particular focus on the following:

- Continue to work together to begin planning now for what will be a very large-scale return process to damaged and destroyed HLP.
- As done in a number of other countries post-conflict, large numbers of similar claims can be grouped into categories where a single legal decision is rendered for entire category, instead of deciding restitution and compensation cases one-by-one in a court setting.
- Allow claimants to use other forms of evidence to prove where they lived—also an international best practice. The UN's 'Pinheiro Principles' encourage countries to accept a wide range of evidence regarding property ownership after a war.¹²⁸
- Leverage civil-military cooperation to manage the return and restitution/compensation process. This can include humanitarian assistance during large-scale returns, assistance in implementation of HLP restitution/compensation decisions and remedies, training, security in areas where population returns take place, and operating the overall process at-scale.

¹²⁶ Anja Karadeglija, "Canada could set global precedent in attempt to redistribute oligarch's millions," *The National Post*, December 29, 2022, <https://nationalpost.com/news/politics/canada-redistribute-oligarchs-millions> (accessed January 23, 2023).

¹²⁷ Redress, *Sanction. Confiscate. Compensate. Briefing: Comparative Laws for Confiscating and Repurposing Russian Oligarch Assets*, (London, UK: Redress, 2022), <https://redress.org/news/briefing-paper-on-comparative-laws-for-confiscating-and-repurposing-russian-oligarch-assets/> (accessed February 2, 2023).

¹²⁸ The Centre on Housing Rights and Evictions (COHRE), *The Pinheiro Principles: United Nations Principles on Housing and Property Restitution for Refugees and Displaced Person*, <https://2001-2009.state.gov/documents/organization/99774.pdf> (accessed January 23, 2023).

- Use Western governments and intelligence efforts to discover the ‘ultimate beneficial owner’ (UBO) of assets usable for repurposing and the reconstruction effort in Ukraine.¹²⁹

Neglect of HLP restitution and compensation for Ukraine’s displaced population carries risks for stability, while creating space for opportunist political actors (internal or external to Ukraine) to take advantage of population-wide grievances. At the same time Ukraine’s technological sophistication and a willing government; and Russia’s frozen assets in the West offer real opportunity to establish a much-improved HLP restitution and compensation process.

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What Gets Protected? Information and Technology. *While speaking at the UN Security Council (UNSC) Open Debate on Protection of Civilians in late May 2022, Robert Mardini, Director-General, International Committee of the Red Cross, enjoined States “to avoid and prevent the spread of mis- and disinformation...and mitigate its impact on affected people.”¹³⁰ Closely related to the information category of POC/CHMR is the discussion of technology. As seen in the two Lessons in this section, technical and informational innovations prove to have both risks and benefits to the civilian protection paradigm.*

(Dis)(Mis) and (Mal) Information Operations and International Humanitarian Law (IHL) (JLLIS ID# 235231)

Observation

In late May 2022, Robert Mardini, Director-General, International Committee of the Red Cross, spoke to the *UN Security Council (UNSC) Open Debate on Protection of Civilians*. In his remarks, he asked the UNSC to address three aspects of the *Protection of Civilians* (POC) concept. Two of the three are generally well-understood by the policy and practitioner community engaged in the Protection discourse of the past several decades: “To make the protection of civilians a strategic priority...in populated areas, which includes avoiding the use of heavy explosive weapons,” and “to ensure accountability for victims without compromising the neutral and humanitarian space...”.¹³¹

The third aspect, “to avoid and prevent the spread of mis- and disinformation...and mitigate its impact on affected people,”¹³² is not as well understood nor as codified in the *Protection of*

¹²⁹ Lesson author’s note: Ascertaining the UBO of an asset or transaction involving those who wish to remain hidden, is an ongoing priority for those concerned with financial crimes, financing terrorism, or illegally hiding financial assets or transactions.

¹³⁰ Robert Mardini, “Briefing to UN Security Council Open Debate on Protection of Civilians,” *International Committee of the Red Cross*, May 25, 2022, <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/deliberate-attacks-on-civilians-causing-untold-suffering> (accessed July 1, 2022).

¹³¹ Robert Mardini, “Briefing to UN Security Council Open Debate on Protection of Civilians,” *International Committee of the Red Cross*, May 25, 2022, <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/deliberate-attacks-on-civilians-causing-untold-suffering> (accessed July 1, 2022).

¹³² *Ibid.*